

Training courses and materials for a research ethics and integrity informed green transition in Europe: a scoping review and gap analysis

Appendix B: Amended search strategy - update 06.08.24

Search strategy – step 1: automated batch querying of European university websites and online training databases using the Lippmannian Device

Searches 1 - 5

Input URLs: University websites batches 1 – 5 [i.e. Search 1: Austria-Finland, search 2: France-Greece, etc.] [for specific websites, please see Table 1-5 below](#)

Input query: (Research OR Science OR Technology OR Innovation OR “Research Integrity” OR “Research Ethics” OR “Responsible Conduct of Research” OR “RCR” OR “Responsible Research and Innovation” OR “RRI”) AND (Sustainable OR Climate OR Environment OR Green) AND (Course OR Module OR Workshop OR Lecture OR Seminar OR Training)

Search Engine: Google

Date range: 01/09/2022 - 06/08/2024

Maximum number of results per website: 30

Searches 6 - 10

Input URLs: University websites batches 1 – 5 [i.e. Search 6: Austria-Finland, search 7: France-Greece, etc.] [for specific websites, please see Table 1-5 below](#)

Input query: (Research OR Science OR Technology OR Innovation OR “Research Integrity” OR “Research Ethics” OR “Responsible Conduct of Research” OR “RCR” OR “Responsible Research and Innovation” OR “RRI”) AND (Sustainable OR Climate OR Environment OR Green) AND (Bachelor OR Minor OR Master OR PhD OR Doctorate OR Program)

Search Engine: Google

Date range: 01/09/2022 - 06/08/2024

Maximum number of results per website: 30

Search 11

Input URLs: Databases [for specific websites, please see Table 6 below](#)

Input query: (Research OR Science OR Technology OR Innovation OR “Research Integrity” OR “Research Ethics” OR “Responsible Conduct of Research” OR “RCR” OR “Responsible Research and

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Innovation" OR "RRI") AND (Sustainable OR Climate OR Environment OR Green OR "Environmental Ethics" OR "Climate Ethics")

Search Engine: Google

Date range: 01/09/2015 - 06/08/2024

Maximum number of results per website: 100

Search strategy – step 2: web scraping using the Search Engine Scraper

Searches 12 - 38

Input query: ("Research" OR "Science" OR "Technology" OR "Innovation") AND ("Integrity" OR "Ethics" OR "Responsible") AND ("Sustainable" OR "Sustainability" OR "Climate" OR "Environment" OR "Environmental" OR "Green") AND ("Course" OR "Module" OR "Lecture" OR "Bachelor" OR "Master" OR "PhD" OR "Training")

Search Engine: Google

Date range: 01/09/2015 - 29/07/2024

Maximum number of results per website: 200

Region: ERA countries [i.e. Search 12: Austria, search 13: Belgium, search 14: Bulgaria, etc.] [for specific regions, please see Table 7 below](#)

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Table 1: University websites batch 1

Country	Universities	English website
Austria	University of Vienna	https://www.univie.ac.at
	Medical University of Graz	https://www.medunigraz.at
	Medical University of Vienna	https://www.meduniwien.ac.at
	Medical University of Innsbruck	https://www.i-med.ac.at
	TU Wien	https://www.tuwien.at
	University of Innsbruck	https://www.uibk.ac.at
	Johannes Kepler University of Linz	https://www.jku.at
	University of Graz	https://www.uni-graz.at
	Graz University of Technology	https://www.tugraz.at
	University of Klagenfurt	https://www.aau.at
	Paris Lodron Universität Salzburg	https://www.plus.ac.at
Montanuniversität Leoben	https://www.unileoben.ac.at	
Belgium	KU Leuven	https://www.kuleuven.be
	Ghent University	https://www.ugent.be
	University of Antwerp	https://www.uantwerpen.be
	Université Catholique de Louvain	https://uclouvain.be
	Université Libre de Bruxelles	https://www.ulb.be
	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	https://www.vub.be
	University of Liège	https://www.uliege.be
	Hasselt University	https://www.uhasselt.be
	University of Mons	https://web.umons.ac.be
	University of Namur	https://www.unamur.be
Bulgaria	Medical University of Sofia	https://mu-sofia.bg
	Sofia University	https://www.uni-sofia.bg
	Technical University of Sofia	https://www.tu-sofia.bg
Croatia	University of Zagreb	https://www.unizg.hr

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	The Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek	https://www.unios.hr
	University of Rijeka	https://uniri.hr
	University of Split	https://www.unist.hr
Republic of Cyprus	University of Cyprus	https://www.ucy.ac.cy
	University of Nicosia	https://www.unic.ac.cy
	Cyprus University of Technology Eastern Mediterranean University	https://www.cut.ac.cy
	Near East University	https://neu.edu.tr
Czech Republic	Charles University	https://cuni.cz
	Masaryk University	https://www.muni.cz
	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)	https://www.czu.cz
	Palacký University Olomouc	https://www.upol.cz
	Brno University of Technology	https://www.vut.cz
	University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague	https://www.vscht.cz
	Czech Technical University in Prague	https://www.cvut.cz
	University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice	https://www.jcu.cz
	University of Hradec Králové	https://www.uhk.cz
	Mendel University in Brno	https://mendelu.cz
	Tomas Bata University in Zlín	https://www.utb.cz
	VSB - Technical University of Ostrava	https://www.vsb.cz
	University of West Bohemia	https://www.zcu.cz
	Jan Evangelista Purkyně University	https://www.ujep.cz
	University of Ostrava	https://www.osu.eu
	University of Pardubice	https://www.upce.cz
	Prague University of Economics and Business	https://www.vse.cz

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	Technical University of Liberec	https://www.tul.cz
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	https://www.ku.dk
	Aarhus University	https://international.au.dk
	Technical University of Denmark	https://www.dtu.dk
	Aalborg University	https://www.en.aau.dk
	University of Southern Denmark	https://www.sdu.dk
	Copenhagen Business School	https://www.cbs.dk
	Roskilde University	https://ruc.dk
Estonia	University of Tartu	https://ut.ee
	Tallinn University of Technology	https://taltech.ee
	Tallinn University	https://www.tlu.ee
Finland	University of Helsinki	https://www.helsinki.fi
	Aalto University	https://www.aalto.fi
	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology LUT	https://www.lut.fi
	University of Oulu	https://www.oulu.fi
	Tampere University	https://www.tuni.fi
	University of Turku	https://www.utu.fi
	University of Jyväskylä	https://www.jyu.fi
	University of Vaasa	https://www.uwasa.fi
	Åbo Akademi University	https://www.abo.fi
University of Eastern Finland	https://www.uef.fi	

Table 2: University websites batch 2

France	Paris Sciences et Lettres – PSL	https://psl.eu
	Research University Paris	https://www.universite-paris-saclay.fr
	Université Paris-Saclay	https://www.universite-paris-saclay.fr
	Institut Polytechnique de Paris	https://www.ip-paris.fr
	Sorbonne University	https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr
	Université Paris Cité	https://u-paris.fr
	École Normale Supérieure de Lyon	https://www.ens-lyon.fr
	Université Grenoble Alpes	https://www.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr
	Montpellier University	https://www.umontpellier.fr
	Aix-Marseille University	https://www.univ-amu.fr
	University of Bordeaux	https://www.u-bordeaux.fr
	Centrale Nantes	https://www.ec-nantes.fr
	Claude Bernard University Lyon 1	https://www.univ-lyon1.fr
	École des Ponts ParisTech	https://ecoledesponts.fr
	IMT Atlantique	https://www.imt-atlantique.fr
	Institut Agro	https://www.institut-agro.fr
	University of Toulouse	https://www.univ-toulouse.fr
	University of Côte d’Azur	https://univ-cotedazur.eu
	ENSTA Bretagne	https://www.ensta-bretagne.fr
	Nantes Université	https://www.univ-nantes.fr
Sciences Po	https://www.sciencespo.fr	
École Centrale de Lyon	https://www.ec-lyon.fr	
École des Mines de Saint-Étienne	https://www.mines-stetienne.fr	
École Nationale des Travaux Publics de l’État (ENTPE)	https://www.entpe.fr	
University of Lille	https://www.univ-lille.fr	

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University of Lorraine	https://www.univ-lorraine.fr
National Institute of Applied Sciences of Lyon (INSA Lyon)	https://www.insa-lyon.fr
Arts et Métiers	https://www.artsetmetiers.fr
Université de Bretagne Occidentale	https://univ-brest.fr
University of Clermont Auvergne	https://www.uca.fr
CY Cergy Paris University	https://www.cyu.fr
Panthéon-Sorbonne University – Paris 1	https://www.pantheonsorbonne.fr
Université de Poitiers	https://www.univ-poitiers.fr
University of Rennes 1	https://www.univ-rennes.fr
University of Tours	https://international.univ-tours.fr
University of Franche-Comté	https://www.univ-fcomte.fr
IMT Nord Europe	https://imt-nord-europe.fr
University of Technology of Troyes	https://www.utt.fr
Université Polytechnique Hauts-de-France	https://www.uphf.fr
Lumière University, Lyon 2	https://welcome.univ-lyon2.fr
Paris Nanterre University	https://university.parisnanterre.fr
University of Pau and Pays de l'Adour	https://www.univ-pau.fr
Université Sorbonne Nouvelle	http://www.univ-paris3.fr
University of Technology of Compiègne	https://www.utc.fr
Jean Moulin University – Lyon 3	https://www.univ-lyon3.fr
Panthéon-Assas University (Paris 2)	https://www.assas-universite.fr
Université de Strasbourg	https://www.unistra.fr
Université Paul Sabatier Toulouse III	https://www.univ-tlse3.fr
Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	https://www.ut-capitole.fr

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	Paul Valéry University Montpellier	https://www.univ-montp3.fr
	Université de Caen Normandie	https://welcome.unicaen.fr
	Université Toulouse - Jean Jaurès	https://www.univ-tlse2.fr
	Université de Limoges	https://www.unilim.fr
	Université Paris 13 Nord	https://www.univ-spn.fr
Germany	Technical University of Munich	https://www.tum.de
	LMU Munich	https://www.lmu.de
	Universität Heidelberg	https://www.uni-heidelberg.de
	Humboldt University of Berlin	https://www.hu-berlin.de
	RWTH Aachen University	https://www.rwth-aachen.de
	University of Bonn	https://www.uni-bonn.de
	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin	https://www.charite.de
	University of Tübingen	https://uni-tuebingen.de
	Free University of Berlin	https://www.fu-berlin.de
	University of Göttingen	https://www.uni-goettingen.de
	University of Freiburg	https://uni-freiburg.de
	University of Hamburg	https://www.uni-hamburg.de
	Technical University of Berlin	https://www.tu.berlin
	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	https://www.kit.edu
	University of Cologne	https://portal.uni-koeln.de
	TU Dresden	https://tu-dresden.de
	University of Würzburg	https://www.uni-wuerzburg.de
	University of Mannheim	https://www.uni-mannheim.de
	University of Erlangen- Nuremberg	https://www.fau.eu
	University of Münster	https://www.uni-muenster.de
	Ulm University	https://www.uni-ulm.de

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Friedrich Schiller University Jena	https://www.uni-jena.de
Goethe University Frankfurt	https://www.goethe-university-frankfurt.de
University of Potsdam	https://www.uni-potsdam.de
Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf	https://www.hhu.de
University of Hohenheim	https://www.uni-hohenheim.de
Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz	https://www.uni-mainz.de
University of Konstanz	https://www.uni-konstanz.de
Ruhr University Bochum	https://www.ruhr-uni-bochum.de
University of Stuttgart	https://www.uni-stuttgart.de
Technical University of Darmstadt	https://www.tu-darmstadt.de
University of Bremen	https://www.uni-bremen.de
University of Kiel	https://www.uni-kiel.de
University of Bayreuth	https://www.uni-bayreuth.de
Justus Liebig University Giessen	https://www.uni-giessen.de
Leibniz University Hannover	https://www.uni-hannover.de
Constructor University	https://constructor.university
University of Greifswald	https://www.uni-greifswald.de
University of Marburg	https://www.uni-marburg.de
University of Passau	https://www.uni-passau.de
TU Dortmund University	https://www.tu-dortmund.de
Hamburg University of Technology	https://www.tuhh.de
Leuphana University of Lüneburg	https://www.leuphana.de
TU Braunschweig	https://www.tu-braunschweig.de
University of Wuppertal	https://www.uni-wuppertal.de
University of Kaiserslautern	https://rptu.de

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	Otto von Guericke University of Magdeburg	https://www.ovgu.de
	University of Siegen	https://www.uni-siegen.de
	Technische Universität Ilmenau	https://www.tu-ilmenau.de
	Universität Leipzig	https://www.uni-leipzig.de
	Saarland University	https://www.uni-saarland.de
	Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg	https://www.uni-halle.de
	Universität Regensburg	https://www.uni-regensburg.de
	Universität Rostock	https://www.uni-rostock.de
	Universität Duisburg-Essen	https://www.uni-due.de
	Bielefeld University	https://www.uni-bielefeld.de
	Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg	https://tu-freiberg.de
Greece	University of Crete	https://www.uoc.gr
	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	https://www.uoa.gr
	Harokopio University of Athens	https://www.hua.gr
	National Technical University of Athens	https://www.ntua.gr
	University of the Aegean	https://www.aegean.edu
	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	https://www.auth.gr
	Athens University of Economics and Business	https://www.aueb.gr
	University of Patras	https://www.upatras.gr
	Democritus University of Thrace	https://duth.gr
	University of Ioannina	https://uoi.gr
	Technical University of Crete	https://www.tuc.gr
	University of Western Macedonia	https://www.uowm.gr
	Hellenic Open University	https://www.eap.gr
	International Hellenic University	https://www.ihu.gr

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University of the Peloponnese

<https://studyingreece.edu.gr/universities/uop>

University of West Attica

<https://www.uniwa.gr>

Table 3: University websites batch 3

Hungary	Semmelweis University	https://semmelweis.hu
	University of Debrecen	https://www.edu.unideb.hu
	Eötvös Loránd University	https://www.elte.hu
	Óbuda University	https://uni-obuda.hu
	University of Pécs	https://international.pte.hu
	University of Szeged	https://u-szeged.hu
	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	https://www.bme.hu
	Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences	https://en.uni-mate.hu
	University of Miskolc	https://en.uni-miskolc.hu
	University of Pannonia	https://international.uni-pannon.hu
	Széchenyi István University	https://admissions.sze.hu
Corvinus University of Budapest	https://www.uni-corvinus.hu	
Ireland	Trinity College Dublin	https://www.tcd.ie
	University College Dublin	https://www.ucd.ie
	RCSI University of Medicine and Health Sciences	https://www.rcsi.com/dublin/about/faculty-of-medicine-and-health-sciences
	University of Galway	https://www.universityofgalway.ie
	University College Cork	https://www.ucc.ie
	Dublin City University	https://www.dcu.ie
	University of Limerick	https://www.ul.ie
	Maynooth University	https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie
	Technological University Dublin	https://www.tudublin.ie
Italy	University of Bologna	https://www.unibo.it
	Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa	https://www.sns.it
	Sapienza University of Rome	https://www.uniroma1.it

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University of Padua	https://www.unipd.it
Politecnico di Milano	https://www.polimi.it
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies – Pisa	https://www.santannapisa.it
Humanitas University Vita-Salute San Raffaele University	https://www.hunimed.eu
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	https://www.unicatt.eu
University of Pavia	https://web-en.unipv.it
University of Rome II – Tor Vergata	https://web.uniroma2.it
University of Florence	https://www.unifi.it
Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	https://www.unibz.it
University of Milan	https://www.unimi.it
University of Milan-Bicocca	https://www.unimib.it
University of Naples Federico II	https://www.international.unina.it
University of Trento	https://www.unitn.it
University of Brescia	https://www.unibs.it
Campus Bio-Medico University of Rome	https://www.unicampus.it
University of Catania	https://www.unict.it
University of Genoa	https://unige.it
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	https://international.unimore.it
University of Pisa	https://www.unipi.it
Polytechnic University of Turin	https://www.polito.it
University of Turin	https://www.unito.it
Verona University	https://www.univr.it
University of L'Aquila	https://www.univaq.it
Ca' Foscari University of Venice	https://www.unive.it

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University of Calabria	https://www.unical.it
University of Ferrara	https://www.unife.it
University of Messina	https://international.unime.it
Polytechnic University of Bari	http://www.en.poliba.it
University of Salerno	https://web.unisa.it
University of Siena	https://www.unisi.it
University of Trieste	https://portale.units.it
Amedeo Avogadro University of Eastern Piedmont	https://www.uniupo.it
University of Bari Aldo Moro	https://www.uniba.it
University of Campania Luigi Vanvitelli	https://international.unicampania.it
University of Foggia	https://www.unifg.it
Gabriele d'Annunzio University	https://www.unich.it
University of Insubria	https://www.uninsubria.eu
Marche Polytechnic University	https://www.univpm.it
University of Palermo	https://www.unipa.it
University of Parma	https://www.unipr.it
Parthenope University of Naples	https://international.uniparthenope.it
University of Rome III	https://www.uniroma3.it
University of Salento	https://international.unisalento.it
University of Sannio	https://www.unisannio.it
University of Sassari	https://www.uniss.it
University of Tuscia	https://www.unitus.it
University of Udine	https://www.uniud.it
University of Bergamo	https://www.unibg.it
University of Camerino (Unicam)	https://international.unicam.it
Kore University of Enna	https://unikore.it

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	University of Urbino Carlo Bo	https://www.uniurb.it
	University of Macerata (UNIMC)	https://www.unimc.it
	Università degli Studi di Perugia	https://www.unipg.it
Latvia	University of Latvia	https://www.lu.lv
	Riga Technical University	https://www.rtu.lv
	Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies	https://www.lbtu.lv
	Riga Stradiņš University	https://www.rsu.lv

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Table 4: University websites batch 4

Lithuania	Lithuanian University of Health Sciences	https://lsmu.lt
	Vilnius University	https://www.vu.lt
	Kaunas University of Technology	https://ktu.edu/
	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Vilnius Tech)	https://vilniustech.lt
	Vytautas Magnus University	https://www.vdu.lt
	Mykolas Romeris University	https://www.mruni.eu
Luxembourg	University of Luxembourg	https://www.uni.lu
Malta	University of Malta	https://www.um.edu.mt
Netherlands	Delft University of Technology	https://www.tudelft.nl
	University of Amsterdam	https://www.uva.nl
	Utrecht University	https://www.uu.nl
	Eindhoven University of Technology	https://www.tue.nl
	Leiden University	https://www.universiteitleiden.nl
	University of Groningen	https://www.rug.nl
	Wageningen University & Research	https://www.wur.nl
	Erasmus University Rotterdam	https://www.eur.nl
	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	https://vu.nl
	University of Twente	https://www.utwente.nl
	Radboud University	https://www.ru.nl
	Maastricht University	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl
	Tilburg University	https://www.tilburguniversity.edu
Poland	Jagiellonian University	https://www.uj.edu.pl
	University of Warsaw	https://www.uw.edu.pl
	Wroclaw Medical University	https://www.umw.edu.pl
	Medical University of Lodz	https://umed.pl

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Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań	https://amu.edu.pl
AGH University of Krakow	https://www.agh.edu.pl
Gdańsk University of Technology	https://pg.edu.pl
Medical University of Białystok	https://www.umb.edu.pl
Medical University of Gdańsk	https://mug.edu.pl
Medical University of Warsaw	https://www.wum.edu.pl
Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń	https://www.umk.pl
Poznan University of Medical Sciences	https://pums.ump.edu.pl
SWPS University	https://swps.pl
University of Wrocław	https://uwr.edu.pl
University of Gdańsk	https://ug.edu.pl
The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin	https://www.kul.pl
Lodz University of Technology	https://p.lodz.pl
Medical University of Lublin	https://umlub.pl
Medical University of Silesia in Katowice	https://smk.sum.edu.pl
Opole University of Technology	https://po.edu.pl
Poznań University of Life Sciences	https://skylark.up.poznan.pl
Poznan University of Technology	https://www.put.poznan.pl
Silesian University of Technology	https://www.polsl.pl
Warsaw University of Life Sciences – SGGW	https://www.sggw.edu.pl
Warsaw University of Technology	https://www.pw.edu.pl
Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences	https://upwr.edu.pl
Wrocław University of Science and Technology	https://pwr.edu.pl
Białystok University of Technology	https://pb.edu.pl
Cracow University of Technology	https://www.pk.edu.pl

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	Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce	https://ujk.edu.pl
	University of Life Sciences in Lublin	https://up.lublin.pl
	University of Lodz	https://www.uni.lodz.pl
	Maria Curie-Skłodowska University (UMCS)	https://www.umcs.pl
	Rzeszów University of Technology	https://w.prz.edu.pl
	SGH Warsaw School of Economics	https://www.sgh.waw.pl
	University of Silesia in Katowice	https://us.edu.pl
	University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn	https://uwm.edu.pl
	Technical University of Lublin	https://pollub.pl
	University of Białystok	https://uwb.edu.pl
	University of Rzeszów	https://www.ur.edu.pl
Portugal	University of Coimbra	https://www.uc.pt
	University of Lisbon	https://www.ulisboa.pt
	University of Porto	https://www.up.pt
	NOVA University of Lisbon	https://www.unl.pt
	University of Aveiro	https://www.ua.pt
	University of Beira Interior	https://www.ubi.pt
	ISCTE-University Institute of Lisbon	https://www.iscte-iul.pt
	University of Minho	https://www.uminho.pt
	University of Algarve	https://www.ualg.pt
	Catholic University of Portugal	https://www.ucp.pt
	University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro	https://www.utad.pt
	Instituto Politécnico de Bragança	https://portal3.ipb.pt/index.php/pt/ipb
	Universidade Lusófona	https://www.ulusofona.pt
	Polytechnic Institute of Porto	https://www.estg.ipp.pt
	Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo	https://www.ipvc.pt

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Romania	Bucharest University of Economic Studies	https://international.ase.ro
	University of Medicine and Pharmacy Carol Davila	https://umfcd.ro
	Babeş-Bolyai University	https://www.ubbcluj.ro
	University of Bucharest	https://unibuc.ro
	Iuliu Hațieganu University of Medicine and Pharmacy Cluj-Napoca	https://umfcluj.ro
	USAMV Cluj-Napoca	https://www.usamvcluj.ro
	George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures	https://edu.umch.de
	University of Medicine and Pharmacy of Craiova	https://www.umfcv.ro
	University of Oradea	https://www.uoradea.ro
	Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava	https://usv.ro
	Technical University of Cluj-Napoca	https://www.utcluj.ro
	Transilvania University of Brașov	https://www.unitbv.ro
	West University of Timișoara	https://www.uvt.ro
	Alexandru Ioan Cuza University	https://www.uaic.ro
	University of Craiova	https://www.ucv.ro
	Dunarea de Jos University of Galati	https://www.ugal.ro
	Gheorghe Asachi Technical University of Iași	https://www.tuiasi.ro
	Grigore T. Popa University of Medicine and Pharmacy	https://www.umfiasi.ro
	Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu	https://www.ulbsibiu.ro
	Ovidius University of Constanța	https://univ-ovidius.ro/
Polytechnic University of Bucharest	https://upb.ro	
Polytechnic University of Timișoara	https://www.upt.ro	
Slovakia	Comenius University in Bratislava	https://uniba.sk
	University of Žilina	https://www.uniza.sk

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	Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice	https://www.upjs.sk
	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra	https://www.uniag.sk
	Technical University of Košice	https://www.tuke.sk
	Matej Bel University	https://www.umb.sk
	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava	https://www.stuba.sk
Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	https://www.uni-lj.si
	University of Maribor	https://www.um.si
	University of Primorska	https://www.upr.si

Table 5: University websites batch 5

Spain	University of Barcelona	https://web.ub.edu
	Autonomous University of Barcelona	https://www.uab.cat
	Pompeu Fabra University	https://www.upf.edu
	University of Navarra	https://www.unav.edu
	Autonomous University of Madrid	https://www.uam.es
	Complutense University of Madrid	https://www.ucm.es
	University of Granada	https://www.ugr.es
	Rovira i Virgili University	https://www.urv.cat
	University of Valencia	https://www.uv.es
	University of the Basque Country	https://www.ehu.eus
	University of Córdoba	https://www.uco.es
	Open University of Catalonia	https://www.uoc.edu
	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	https://www.upc.edu
	Polytechnic University of Valencia	https://www.upv.es
	Universitat Ramon Llull	https://www.url.edu
	University of Santiago de Compostela	https://www.usc.gal
	University of Alcalá	https://www.uah.es
	University of the Balearic Islands	https://www.uib.eu
	Carlos III University of Madrid	https://www.uc3m.es
	University of Castilla-La Mancha	https://www.uclm.es
University of Deusto	https://www.deusto.es	
University of Girona	https://www.udg.edu	
Universitat Internacional de Catalunya	https://www.uic.es	
University of Jaén	https://www.ujaen.es	

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Jaume I University	https://www.uji.es
University of Lleida	https://www.udl.cat
University of Murcia	https://www.um.es
University of Oviedo	https://www.uniovi.es
Pablo de Olavide University	https://www.upo.es
University of Salamanca	https://www.usal.es
University of Seville	https://www.us.es
Technical University of Madrid	https://www.upm.es
University of Vic – Central	
University of Catalonia	https://www.uvic.cat
University of Vigo	https://www.uvigo.gal
University of Zaragoza	https://www.unizar.es
University of A Coruña	https://www.udc.es
University of Alicante	https://www.ua.es
University of Almería	https://www.ual.es
University of Cadiz	https://www.uca.es
European University of Madrid	https://universidadeuropea.com
University of Extremadura	https://www.unex.es
University of La Laguna	https://www.ull.es
University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	https://www.ulpgc.es
University of León	https://www.unileon.es
University of Malaga	https://www.uma.es
Miguel Hernández University of Elche	https://www.umh.es
Public University of Navarre	https://www.unavarra.es
Technical University of Cartagena	https://www.upct.es
University of Burgos	https://www.ubu.es

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	Universidad Católica San Antonio de Murcia (UCAM)	https://international.ucam.edu
	Universidad Loyola	https://www.uloyola.es
	National University of Distance Education (UNED)	https://www.uned.es
	University Rey Juan Carlos	https://en.urjc.es
	UNIR – International University of La Rioja	https://www.unir.net https://universityofvalladolid.uva.es
	University of Valladolid	a.es
	Comillas Pontifical University	https://www.comillas.edu
	Universidad Instituto de Empresa (IE University)	https://www.ie.edu/es https://www.ceuuniversities.com
	CEU Educational Group	m
Sweden	Karolinska Institute	https://ki.se
	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	https://www.kth.se
	Lund University	https://www.lunduniversity.lu.se
	Uppsala University	https://www.uu.se
	Stockholm University	https://www.su.se
	Chalmers University of Technology	https://www.chalmers.se
	University of Gothenburg	https://www.gu.se
	Linköping University	https://liu.se
	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	https://www.slu.se
	Umeå University	https://www.umu.se
	Jönköping University	https://ju.se
	Örebro University	https://www.oru.se
	Karlstad University	https://www.kau.se
	Halmstad University	https://www.hh.se

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Table 6: Databases

Training database/repository	URL
OER Metafinder	https://mom.gmu.edu
Openly Available Sources Integrated Search (OASIS)	https://oasis.geneseo.edu/index.php
Archive	https://archive.org/details/education
Class Central	https://www.classcentral.com/
Edusources	https://edusources.nl/
Khan Academy	https://www.khanacademy.org/
MOOC List	https://www.mooc-list.com/
OpenupEd	https://www.openuped.eu/
Repository of Open and Affordable Materials (ROAM)	https://roam.libraries.psu.edu
Skills Commons	https://www.skillscommons.org/ https://www.unesco.org/en/open-educational-resources
UNESCO Open Educational Resources	https://www.mooc.org/
MOOC.org	https://www.mooc.org/
UNITAR	https://www.unitar.org/free-and-open-courses
FAO elearning Academy	https://elearning.fao.org/
Alison	https://alison.com/
AGORA	https://agora.unicef.org/
Embassy of Good Science	https://embassy.science/wiki/Main_Page
RRI Tools	https://rri-tools.eu/
ROSiE Knowledge Hub	https://rosie-project.eu/rosie-knowledge-hub/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/

Table 7: List of ERA countries

Country

Austria

Belgium

Bulgaria

Croatia

Republic of Cyprus

Czech Republic

Denmark

Estonia

Finland

France

Germany

Greece

Hungary

Ireland

Italy

Latvia

Lithuania

Luxembourg

Malta

Netherlands

Poland

Portugal

Romania

Slovakia

Slovenia

Spain

Sweden